

Deliverable D1:

Guidelines and a test protocol for flow control evaluating leakage and burst pressure in microfluidic devices

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1. Scope

This document presents guidelines and a test protocol for leakage and burst pressure of microfluidic devices. The guidelines and the protocol in this document aim to operate within the following parametric range: non-hazardous water-based flow media, temperature (4-50) °C, pressure below 200 kPa (2000 mbar), and flow rates between 1 and 100 µL/min. The reasoning behind these operational parameters is to frame a subset without risks to safety or the environment. The testing of this document applies to device types that are not capillary flow devices. Furthermore, the testing was demonstrated with a microfluidic device made of COC (cyclic olefin copolymer) and mini Luer connectors. This test protocol originated from the discussions found in activity A1.2.2 (Heeren et al., 2022) and the work by Silverio et al. (Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Furthermore, this test protocol was created from the work of activity A1.2.3, which performed documented examples of leakage testing and burst pressure testing in the liquid flow laboratory at CETIAT (Villeurbanne, France). Activities A1.1.1 and A1.1.2, also contributed to this test protocol with vocabulary for microfluidic components and definitions of flow control terminology (Kartmann et al., 2022; Silverio, Metaxiotou, et al., 2022).

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.2.4 M23	<p>Using input from A1.1.1, A1.1.2, A1.2.2 and A1.2.3, DTI with support from CETIAT, IPQ, INESC MN, CMI, BHT, HSG-IMIT, TUBITAK, NQIS and EnablingMNT will produce guidelines and a test protocol on leakage and burst pressure for flow control in microfluidic devices. These will be shared with the relevant standardisation group such as CEN/TC332/WG7 and/or ISO/TC48/WG3.</p> <p>Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator, on behalf of DTI, CETIAT, IPQ, INESC MN, CMI, BHT, HSG-IMIT, TUBITAK, NQIS and EnablingMNT will submit the guidelines and protocols to EURAMET as D1: '<i>Guidelines and a test protocol for flow control evaluating leakage and burst pressure in microfluidic devices</i>'.</p>	DTI , CETIAT, IPQ, INESC MN, CMI, BHT, HSG-IMIT, TUBITAK, NQIS, EnablingMNT

2. Introduction

This section introduces microfluidics, the need for standardisation of tests in microfluidics, and common test methods for leakage and burst pressure in microfluidics.

2.1. Microfluidics

Microfluidics refers to the technology utilizing miniaturized systems of fluid channels, where the channels have at least one dimension, for example width or height, smaller than 1000 µm (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019; Heeren et al., 2022; Qin et al., 1998). From the perspective of fluid mechanics, a microfluidic channel is small enough that its associated Reynolds number usually falls within the laminar flow regime, where the viscous forces of the fluid dominate over the inertial forces of the fluid (Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Laminar flow is characterized by an orderly and predictable behaviour that to some extent carries over to microfluidic systems, which in turn can implement functionality that may be difficult to realise with macroscale devices (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019).

The development of microfluidics has comparisons with the development of microelectronics (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019). The transistor, which is a fundamental component of electronics, was invented at the Bell Telephone Laboratories in 1947 (Warner, 2001). The integrated circuit, which comprises multiple electronic components manufactured in a single semiconductor crystal, was developed during the late 1950s and early 1960s (Winston, 1988). Following these developments,

microelectronics became a rapidly growing field with extensive commercialization, and mass-produced electronic devices became common for consumers and businesses. In 2000, one half of the Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to Jack Kilby for his contributions to the development of integrated circuits (The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, 2000).

Drawing parallels, microfluidics has origins in microelectronics, and some of the first microfluidic devices were devices for inkjet printing (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019). The first realisation of inkjet printing was in 1965 (Sweet, 1965), and in 1977 an array of multiple inkjet nozzles was manufactured on a single semiconductor wafer (Bassous et al., 1977). Besides inkjet printing, there are other milestones and interesting applications of microfluidics. For example, a microscale system for analysis of gas composition using gas chromatography, which in 1979 was manufactured on a single 5 cm silicon wafer (Terry et al., 1979). Such a system is sometimes referred to as a lab-on-a-chip (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019). The 1990s saw the development of microfluidic chips made of glass rather than semiconductors (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019). Such glass chips with an array of capillary electrophoresis channels helped develop faster and simpler DNA sequencing (Simpson et al., 1998; Woolley & Mathies, 1994), and this technology contributed considerably to the completion of the Human Genome Project in the 1990s and 2000s (Kambara, 2010; Xiong & Cheng, 2007). In the 21st century microfluidic systems denoted organ-on-a-chip were developed, and in these systems the chip contains cultures of living cells to simulate organ tissue (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019). Organ-on-a-chip devices aim to replicate the features that define an organ more accurately than traditional two-dimensional cell cultures, and organ-on-a-chip devices could aid the development and testing of medicine. Further examples and application of microfluidics can be found in the review by Convery & Gadegaard (Convery & Gadegaard, 2019).

As of the early 2020s microfluidics has developed into a diverse field with applications in chemistry, life sciences, and biomedical fields. Over 800 companies are involved in this field as developers and manufacturers of microfluidic devices, which are being used in many laboratories all over the world. For instance, most DNA sequencing equipment is based on microfluidic disposables. The number of microfluidic devices yearly subjected to the FDA for qualification is increasing. All these millions of microfluidic devices and disposables must be tested and qualified. Standard test protocols are therefore needed.

2.2. The need for standardisation of tests

To contribute to the standardisation and consensus of microfluidics, this test protocol aims to present and demonstrate guidelines for testing leakage and burst pressure of microfluidic devices. The state of leakage testing in microfluidics, as of the early 2020s, is discussed by Silverio et al. and Heeren et al. (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). They describe that leakage is one of the most encountered failure modes in microfluidics, and that all microfluidic developers check their devices for leakage. However, many developers use their own in-house protocols for leakage testing. This has been common practise for decades because currently there are no standard test protocols for microfluidics.

Silverio et al. and Heeren et al. discuss the challenges of microfluidic leakage testing and burst pressure testing (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). E.g., it is difficult to detect a leakage and measure a leakage rate because of the small amounts of fluids associated with the devices. The diversity of microfluidics makes it very difficult for a single test protocol to cover all devices, setups, and applications. Also, there are many possibilities for leaks in microfluidics: connections between devices, within microchannels, and at the connections to equipment upstream or downstream of the

microfluidic chip. Depending on the application, for example a medical device, a leakage may be a serious failure that prevents a microfluidic device from functioning correctly and it may compromise safety.

The potential benefits of standardised tests for leakage and burst pressure are discussed by Silverio et al. and Heeren et al. (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Leakage testing with quantitative metrics can provide quality control assessments for phases such as development, manufacturing, and final product. Standardised leakage tests could help identify vulnerabilities in design, and guide iterations of the above phases until a final product that does not leak during handling and operation is achieved. Standardised testing for leakage and burst pressure of final products could also help ensuring that end products will perform safely and as intended.

2.3. Common test methods for leakage and burst pressure

An ensemble of possible test methods for microfluidic leakage testing and burst pressure testing is described by Heeren et al. and Silverio et al. (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Noteworthy test methods are discussed below: visual inspection, liquid pressure decay, gas pressure decay and flow rate. The reader may refer to Heeren et al. and Silverio et al. for further test methods and further discussions hereof (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022).

This test protocol considers that a leakage test applies a temporally constant pressure throughout the system under test and observes the system for leakage over a period. Possible observations or measurements that can infer leakage are discussed in the following. Visual inspection identifies leakage from visual observation of moisture, small drops, or wet surfaces. Here, it is important to avoid false positives from condensation from humid air, which may also form moisture. It can be labour intensive and time consuming to perform visual inspection for leakage testing, and it may take minutes or hours before a leak has spilled enough liquid to be visible.

Liquid pressure decay involves a microfluidic device filled with a test liquid connected to a pressure source and a pressure sensor. All down-stream ports are closed, and the device is pressurised to a specified pressure. The device is then disconnected from the pressure source, and the pressure is monitored for a pressure decay over time. If a pressure decay is observed and all else is equal, this infers the presence of a leakage.

Gas pressure decay uses a gas as test fluid, but otherwise its operation is similar to the liquid pressure decay method. If gas is not the intended medium of the device, it is important to consider the difference between the gas medium and the intended medium. For example, air is expected to leak a 51 times larger amount of fluid than water, if the difference is estimated using their ratio of viscosity. This however does not consider flow rate influencing parameters typically seen in microfluidics. Take for instance capillary forces. It can therefore not be assumed a priori that this 51 times larger rule will be valid for microfluidics.

Flow rate leakage testing is discussed by Silverio et al. (Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). These discussions mention a flow rate sensor used to quantitatively determine a leak and its leakage rate.

This test protocol also considers that a burst pressure test applies an increasing pressure throughout the system under test, and simultaneously observes the system for bursting. The increasing pressure can be steadily ramped up or increased in a series of steps. A burst pressure test determines the pressure at which a component or system fails due to a high internal pressure. A burst is characterised by the rupture of a component, release of the contained fluid, and it is often a sudden and catastrophic failure. A burst pressure test is by nature a destructive test, which determines the maximum pressure

before a burst occurs. For safety reasons, burst tests are performed with a liquid as test medium, and if a gas is used the device under test must be in a containment chamber.

Figure 1 shows a flowchart that aims to guide selection among four test protocols that are classified according to operational parameters of microfluidic applications. The flowchart in Figure 1 was taken from Heeren et al. (Heeren et al., 2022), and the flowchart is discussed further by Heeren et al. and Silverio et al. (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). The classification considers the operational parameters: chemical hazards, pressure, temperature, and type of device. The four protocols classified in Figure 1 are: protocol A for leakage testing of capillary devices, protocol B for leakage testing associated with quality assurance and no risk to the user, protocol C for leakage testing for operational parameters with risk, and protocol D for leakage testing for operational parameters with high risk. This document will not describe the protocols A, C and D further, but instead focus on establishing guidelines and test protocol for protocol B.

Figure 1: A flowchart diagram that uses classification criteria for selecting a suitable leakage test protocol. The chart is reused with permission from Heeren et al. (Heeren et al., 2022), and the chart is copyrighted by the Microfluid Association (The Microfluidics Association, 2022). Notice how the risk for each protocol depends on the operational parameters of the microfluidic device.

As stated earlier in this introduction, the diversity of microfluidics devices is a challenge for creating standardised test protocols for leakage testing and burst pressure testing. According to Silverio et al., one way to approach this challenge is to start developing testing for common device types already in the market and for low-risk operational parameters: non-hazardous water-based flow media, temperature (4-50) °C, pressure below 200 kPa (2000 mbar), and flow rates between 1 and 100 µL/min (Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). As stated in the scope, the reasoning behind these operational parameters is that they frame an operational subset with low risks for operator safety and the environment. In the context of the flowchart of Figure 1, this corresponds to test protocol B. Thus, this test protocol formulates guidelines and documented examples of tests for leakage and burst pressure for protocol B, see Figure 1, and this test protocol uses the test methods: visual inspection, pressure

decay and flow rate measurement. Future work can expand microfluidic testing further, it can develop other test protocols, and explore other methods for testing leakage and burst pressure.

3. Materials and methods

This section on material and methods uses the vocabulary of microfluidic components and definitions of flow control terminology established in activities A1.1.1 and A1.1.2 (Kartmann et al., 2022; Silverio, Metaxiotou, et al., 2022), and ISO/DIS 10991 - Microfluidics — Vocabulary (ISO/TC 48, 2009).

The documented example of this test protocol was performed at the nano-flow primary standard, located in the liquid flow laboratory at CETIAT (Villeurbanne, France), and the microfluidic device used in the tests was a microfluidic chip of the model Fluidic 157 obtained from the Microfluidic ChipShop (Microfluidic ChipShop, 2023). Figure 2 displays two schematic drawings of the chip. The microfluidic chip was made of the material TOPAS, a commercial type of cyclic olefin copolymer (COC), and the chip had 8 parallel channels which were 100 μm wide, 100 μm deep and 18 mm long. The ends of the eight channels were fabricated with integrated ports in the form of female mini Luer ports. A port where a flow entered the chip was denoted an inlet, and a port where a flow could leave the chip was denoted an outlet. The size of the base of the chip was 75.5 mm by 25.5 mm.

Figure 2: Two schematic drawings of the microfluidic chip of the model Fluidic 157 from the Microfluidic ChipShop (Microfluidic ChipShop, 2023). Drawings reused with permission from the Microfluidic ChipShop GmbH (Microfluidic ChipShop, 2002).

Figure 3 shows a photograph of the microfluidic chip (centre and left) mounted for tests at CETIAT in Villeurbanne, France. Also visible in Figure 3 are a Thorlabs translation mount for rectangular optics (centre and lower-left), the lens of a JAI industrial camera (lower-right) and several Upchurch adaptors (upper-right) for connecting the microfluidic chip. In the test setup and the performed tests, the microfluidic chip was referred to as the device under test.

Figure 3: A photograph of the microfluidic chip model Fluidic 157 during testing at CETIAT in Villeurbanne, France.

Figure 4 shows a schematic diagram for the test setup used for the leakage test and burst pressure test, in addition Figure 5 shows two photographs of the test setup.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of the setup for testing of leakage and burst pressure. (F) flow sensor, (P) pressure sensor, (O) outlet of the microfluidic device under test.

Figure 5: Two photographs of the test setup used for the testing of leakage and burst pressure.

The flow generation of the test setup was achieved with an Elveflow OB1 MkII pressure controller with a (0-200) mbar channel and a (0-2000) mbar channel. The liquid propelled by the pressure controller was ultra-pure degassed water (conductivity below 0.06 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, filtered at 0.2 μm), referred to as the test medium. The flow sensor of the test setup alternated between two models of thermal mass flow sensors. The first thermal mass flowmeter was a Bronkhorst L01 with a full range of 1.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and data acquisition via the FlowPlot software. The second mass flow meter was an Elveflow MFS 2 with a full range of 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and data acquisition via the ESI software. The pressure sensor of the test setup was an Elveflow MFP inline microfluidic pressure sensor with 16 bar full range and readings acquired using the ESI software. The camera of the flow setup was used for in-situ flow measurement, and the model of the camera was a JAI SP-12000M-CXP4-F with a 4096x3072 resolution and a maximum frame rate of 189 fps with full resolution. The images of the camera were acquired with the StreamPix Software, and the post processing was done with a homemade Python software for determining the flow rate using a modified form of the image correlation method (Batista et al., 2020; Morgan et al., 2020). Finally, the test setup had a thermo-hygro-barometer of the model ROTRONIC LOG-HC2-P1 / HC2-C05, which recorded the temperature, humidity, and ambient pressure at the location of the test setup. All instruments were calibrated over their full measuring range, and with traceability to national standard at CETIAT laboratory or by ISO17025 accredited laboratories.

Stainless steel 1/16" pipes connected the components of the test setup and made a fluidic path from the pressure controller to the device under test. An assembly of three adaptors connected one inlet of the device under test to the fluidic path of the test setup. This assembly comprised a Luer male to threaded Upchurch adaptor (item number P-683-01), a threaded female-female Upchurch 1/16" OD PEEK elbow (item number P-430), and an Upchurch Flangeless Nut for 1/16" OD (item number P-235). Figure 6 shows two photographs of the adaptors.

Figure 6: Photographs of the adapters that connect the fluidic path of the test setup to the device under test. The photograph on the left is reused with permission from TECHLAB GmbH, Germany (TECHLAB GmbH, 2023).

This test protocol was developed based on the results obtained with three test methods: visual inspection, pressure decay and flow rate, using a liquid test fluid. Prior to all tests the outlet of the device under test had been closed using a Luer plug tightened by hand, and it was insured that the test setup had at least 30 minutes warming time after the power was turned on.

Figure 7: Photographs of the Luer plugs used to close the outlet of the device under test.

In the tests the pressure controller was used to pressurize the test setup throughout the fluidic path, including the device under test, while the specific leakage test performed relevant visual observations or measurements. In the visual inspection test a visual search for moisture, small drops, or wet surfaces on the device under test was made. In the pressure decay test the pressure prior to the inlet of the device under test was measured with the pressure sensor, and leakage may be inferred from decaying values of measured pressure. In the flow rate test the flow rate, and pressure prior to the inlet of the device under test, were measured with the corresponding sensors. In flow rate testing leakage may be inferred from a non-zero flow rate.

3.1. Protocol for leakage tests and burst pressure tests

This document on leakage tests and burst pressure tests formulated the following protocol using the test methods: visual inspection, pressure decay and flow rate. The protocol used the setup described above. Given the consideration about specific pressure operations for leakage tests vs burst pressure tests, see section 2.3, the test protocol presented here has tests with combined leakage test and burst pressure test. As described below, the tests feature steps of increasing pressure. As such, the plateaus

of the steps constitute a series of leakage tests with increasing pressure, and the steps of increasing pressure constitute a burst pressure test. Notice that the outlet of the pressure controller was located upstream from the device under test, and therefore the outlet pressure of the pressure controller was different from the pressure measured prior to the inlet of the device under test. Figure 8 can be consulted for a process flow diagram that summarises the protocol for leakage tests and burst pressure tests.

Figure 8: A process flow diagram summarising protocols for combined tests for leakage and burst pressure with visual inspection, pressure decay and flow rate.

3.1.1. Common startup for visual inspection, pressure decay, and flow rate

Acclimatise all elements of the test setup and the device under test, by leaving them in the room where the test is to be performed for at least 24 hours prior to any testing.

Evaluate the amount of test medium in the reservoir of the pressure controller. If necessary, fill the reservoir at least 30 minutes prior to any testing.

Turn on all electrically powered elements and allow them to warm up for at least 30 minutes prior to any testing.

Mount the test setup by connecting all elements together. Make sure that all fittings are tightly connected, and keep in mind that poor connections may cause leakage. The test setup of this example was connected, as illustrated in Figure 4, using stainless steel 1/16" pipes.

Flush the test setup by circulating the test medium prior to any tests. The flushing is more effective with high flow or high pressure, but both should stay well below the maximum tolerable for the elements of the test setup. Overt time, the circulation will flush out or absorb air bubbles trapped in the internal volume of the elements of the test setup. This is important as trapped air bubbles can compromise accurate measurements of pressure or flow rate. When flushing is complete, stop the circulation.

Close the outlet of the device under test with a plug. In this example the outlet was closed with a Luer plug tightened by hand, see Figure 7.

Confirm that the fluidic path has no flow, and that the pressure has been relieved. Then zero the pressure sensors and flow sensors to minimise any measurement offset.

Start the data acquisition system.

3.1.2. Visual inspection

Set a target pressure for the outlet of the pressure controller. In this example of visual inspection, the initial target pressure was set so the pressure at the inlet of the device under test was approximately 5 mbar. Monitor the outlet pressure of the pressure controller and wait for it to stabilise.

The pressure was kept constant for approximately 55 minutes, during which the device under test was visually inspected for any signs of leakage or burst.

Increase the outlet pressure of the pressure controller. In this example the pressure was increased with a step that increased the inlet pressure of the device under test approximately 8 mbar.

Repeat the two above steps, until the maximum pressure of interest is reached, or leakage or burst is identified. In this example, the test was stopped after a leakage was identified when the inlet pressure at the device under test was approximately 70 mbar.

3.1.3. Pressure decay

Set a target pressure for the outlet of the pressure controller. In this example the initial target pressure was set so the inlet pressure at the device under test was approximately 0 mbar. Monitor the outlet pressure of the pressure controller and wait for it to stabilise.

The pressure controller remained connected to the device under test, while the pressure at the outlet of the pressure controller was kept constant. At the same time, measurements of pressure were made at the inlet of the device under test for approximately 3 minutes.

Increase the outlet pressure of the pressure controller. In this example the pressure was increased with a step, which increased the inlet pressure of the device under test approximately 100 mbar for the first 3 steps, and approximately 200 mbar or more for the following steps.

Repeat the above two steps until the maximum pressure of interest is reached, or leakage or burst is identified.

3.1.4. Flow rate

Set a target pressure for the pressure controller. In this example the initial target pressure was set so the inlet pressure at the device under test was approximately 0 mbar. Monitor the outlet pressure of the pressure controller and wait for it to stabilise.

The pressure controller remained connected to the device under test, and for approximately 3 minutes the outlet pressure was kept constant, and measurements of flow rate were made along with the pressure at the inlet of the device under test.

Increase the outlet pressure of the pressure controller. In this example the pressure was increased with a step that increased the inlet pressure of the device under test approximately 100 mbar for the first 3 steps, and approximately 200 mbar or more for the following steps.

Repeat the two above steps until the maximum pressure of interest is reached, or leakage or burst is identified.

3.1.5. Common ending for visual inspection, pressure decay, and flow rate

When the combined leakage test and burst pressure test has finished, stop the data acquisition and the pressure controller. The device under test can be disconnected and removed from the test setup. If necessary, the test setup can be disassembled.

4. Results

This section presents the results from the protocol tests with visual inspection, pressure decay and flow rate.

4.1. Visual inspection

Figure 9 presents steps of increasing pressure measured prior to the inlet of the device under test.

Figure 9: Pressure measured by the pressure sensor prior to the inlet of the device under test, during visual inspection for a combined leakage test and burst pressure test.

For all but the last pressure step, visual inspection did not find any signs of leakage or burst. Figure 10 presents a photograph of the device under test, where visual inspection has identified a leak at the last step, at approximately 70 mbar.

Figure 10: Visual identification of a leak at the inlet of the device under test during the test of leakage and burst pressure with visual inspection.

4.2. Pressure decay

Figure 11 shows the pressure measured prior to the inlet of the device under test during a pressure decay test. Notice the multiple steps of increasing pressure in Figure 11, and Figure 12 shows a more detailed view of the final step where the pressure was approximately 1400 mbar. A leakage occurred during the last step of 1400 mbar. The existing of this leakage was inferred from the flow rate

measurement shown in Figure 13, and visual observation at the connector at the inlet. There was no evidence from flow rate or visual observation for leakage at the previous pressure steps.

Figure 11: Measured inlet pressure of the device under test during the combined leakage test and burst pressure test by pressure decay.

Figure 12: A more detailed view of the measured pressure at 1400 mbar during the pressure decay test, also seen in Figure 11. It was inferred from flowrate measurements and visual observation that a leakage occurred during the pressure step in this figure, see Figure 13.

4.3. Flow rate

Figure 13 shows measurements of pressure and flow rate from the same leak as observed in Figure 11 and Figure 12. Reiterating, the leakage appeared at the 1400 mbar step, and in Figure 13 the thermal mass flow meter measured a nonzero flow rate, which in effect was the leakage flow rate.

Figure 13: Measurements of inlet pressure and flow rate during the leakage test and burst pressure test with flow rate.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Three test methods were investigated: visual inspection, pressure decay and flow rate. The tests were carried out as combined tests of leakage test and burst pressure test. During the tests, leakages were identified. However, it proved difficult to burst the device under test, as the chip would leak rather than burst. Hence, no results from an actual burst were presented in this protocol. The leak, which prevented a potential burst, happened between the inlet port and the connector. This is probably due to inadequate matching of connection tolerances between the inlet port inner diameter and the outer diameter of the connector. This test protocol made a total of three burst pressure tests, which was most likely too few for a statistically rigorous evaluation the burst pressure test. Future work will attempt a burst on transfer standards currently under development, and the results will be included in the technical report of MFMET activity A2.4.4, which is to be published in May 2024.

Visual inspection convincingly detected a wet surface on the device under test, and not only inferred the existence of a leak but also localized it with high precision, see Figure 10. The ability of visual inspection to accurately identify leaks and precisely localize them is an advantage. However, it is a known disadvantage that visual inspection can be time consuming (Heeren et al., 2022). Indeed, the visual inspection in this example took about 8 hours.

The pressure decay test successfully measured a time series of pressure measurements for various steps of pressure values, see Figure 11 and Figure 12. According to flow rate and visual observation there was no leakage or burst for the first eight pressure steps, while there was a leakage for the last pressure step at approximately 1400 mbar. For this last step, with the leakage, the pressure measurements show more variation than previous steps. First there is a slight increase followed by a slight decrease. It can be argued that the pressure values before and after the decrease were sufficiently different, and hence the leakage was indeed detected by the pressure decay test.

Oppositely, one could argue that variations in pressure values can also be seen for previous steps, for example at approximately 3850 s and approximately 950 mbar in Figure 11. However, it is pointed out that only the final pressure step had collaborating evidence for a leakage, see Figure 13. A disadvantage of the pressure decay test performed in this example, could be that its identification of a leakage was less clear than the visual inspection test and the flow rate test. During the pressure decay test the pressure controller remained connected to the device under test, and the pressure controller kept a constant pressure at the outlet of the pressure controller. An alternative way this could have been operated was to have a valve somewhere between the pressure controller and the pressure sensor, see Figure 4. Once the target pressure had been reached and stabilized the valve could have been shut, which would have disconnected the pressure controller from pressure measurements at the inlet of the device under test (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). This approach could make a clearer distinction between pressure time series data that either goes into a plateau (no leakage) or continues to decrease (leakage). Furthermore, testers should be aware that especially at low pressure virtual leaks, which are explained in the following, could influence the tests. The way virtual leaks work is the following: imaging a dead-end capillary inside the device. When the device is pressurized, this capillary will slowly fill. The difference with a real leak is that for a real leak the pressure will continue to decrease, while for a virtual leak it will flatten out.

The flow rate test successfully measured the flow rate during various steps of increasing pressurisation. For the first eight steps of pressurisation, it measured zero flow rate. As seen in Figure 13, a non-zero flow rate was measured during the last pressure step, where a leakage occurred. The difference between zero flow rate and approximately 450 nL/min was very distinct, and it was convincing that the flow rate test identified the leakage. The total duration of the test by flow rate was approximately 27 minutes, while the last pressure step took approximately 4 minutes. Since the pressure decay and flow rate were measured together, the test by pressure decay had the same duration. Hence the flow rate test, and the pressure decay test, were faster compared to the duration of the visual inspection test. It is an advantage of the tests by flow rate and pressure decay that it is relatively fast to perform them. A possible disadvantage of the tests by flow rate and pressure decay could be that they do not localize the leakage.

Future work may also consider inherent leakage in the test setup and determine this separately from leakage in the microfluidic device under test. One would then need to test the test setup itself, without a microfluidic device, and establish a baseline for the leakage of the test setup. The leakage of connections, for example mini Luer connectors, could also have separate testing.

This test protocol exclusively worked with a microfluidic chip made of the material COC and connections of the type mini Luer connectors. Other types of microfluidic chips exist, for example with the materials PDMS (Polydimethylsiloxane) or glass, as well as different production methods, for example embossing or injection moulding. Connections for different types of microfluidic chips are not universal, and future work could develop guidelines for good and well-sealed connections for different types of chips and connections. Such future guidelines could support the use of standardised testing for different types of microfluidic chips.

When implementing a test setup, for example at a manufacturer of microfluidic devices, there are considerations about how many, and which, devices to test (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). The liquid-based testing described in this test protocol could be unacceptable for microfluidic chips that have requirements regarding low contamination, sterilisation, or single-use devices. In such cases liquid-based testing can be a destructive test, and it is not possible to test every single device. Instead, a manufactured lot can be statistically sampled for a subset of devices for testing. Statistical approaches can be used to validate the number of tests needed to demonstrate compliance (Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Testing with a gas medium can be non-destructive, and sometimes enable reuse

of a device after testing (Heeren et al., 2022). As many microfluidic devices use liquids, liquid-based testing can have the advantage of being closer to the actual application.

In the context of Figure 1, the tests of this protocol classify as protocol B, which are tests for quality assurance. Furthermore, the tests of this protocol used a liquid test medium, ultra-pure degassed water. Future work may expand leakage testing and burst pressure testing for microfluidics further, and design other test protocols with different test medium, for example gas mediums, and test protocols for applications with capillary devices or situations with and without risk or high risk (Heeren et al., 2022; Silverio, Guha, et al., 2022). Future work can also present results from tests where an actual burst was achieved.

Three examples of leakage tests and burst pressure tests in microfluidics were performed, and Table 1 summarises their advantages and disadvantages. Visual inspection and flow rate convincingly identified a leakage. Pressure decay test was perhaps less convincing in identifying a leakage, but this could be improved by changing the mode of operation and by using a valve, as discussed above. The advantages and disadvantages of different test methods were discussed in relation to duration and leakage localisation. In conclusion, this example demonstrated and documented three methods for leakage test and burst pressure test and formulated them as a test protocol. In section 3, the test protocol is presented in the form of guidelines and a compact process flow diagram. Practitioners of microfluidics can consult these guidelines for a reference on how leakage tests and burst pressure tests could be performed and find inspiration to test setups and parameters for the operation of tests.

Table 1: This table presents advantages and disadvantages of the investigated test methods.

Test method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Visual inspection	Localization of leak	Time consuming
	Highly convincing results	
Pressure decay	Faster to execute	The test performed in this guideline, could have more convincing results
		Virtual leaks
Flow rate	Faster to execute	Requires a flow meter for microfluidics
	Highly convincing results	

6. References

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